

DEVELOPING WRITING SKILLS AT ELEMENTARY LEVEL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7256294>

ANNOTATION: This article highlights the strategies of writing and recommendations about teaching writing skills at early stages of learning foreign languages. And offers some clues on developing writing skills of young learners.

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqolada chet tilini o'rganuvchilarga yozuvni o'rgatishning samarali strategiyalari yoritilib, bu borada muayyan tavsiyalar berilgan. O'quvchilarda yozuv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish uchun e'tiborga molik jihatlarni taklif qiladi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: yozuv, mahorat, talaba, o'quvchi, o'ziga ishonch, aloqa, rivojlanish, fikrini bayon qila olish, yodlash, rivojlanish, mashq qilish, muvaffaqiyatli yozuvchilar, mashqlar, to'g'ri yozish, ruhlantirish, talaffuz, lug'at, qo'lda yozish, gap tuzish, strategiya, baholash.

KEY WORDS: writing, skill, student, child, self-confidence, communication, developing, self-expression, learning, develop, practice, effective writers, successful writer, spelling, activities, encourage, pronounce, dictionary, handwriting, sentence construction, strategy, evaluate

“Writing today is not a frill for the few, but an essential skill for the language learner.

Writing is a process in which writer composes a text. Writing is not a straight process as going out or walking. It is variable in style. Writing is a priceless and very important tool for communication, language learning and self-expression of thoughts and ideas. People who do not have excellent writing skills may have some troubles in education and employment as well. The language learners should develop an early foundation in writing in order not to have such problems. A student who has good writing skills can communicate with self-confidence and express his ideas effectively and efficiently.

According to some authors, students who develop strong writing skills at an early age acquire a good tool for communication, self-expression and learning. Such skills will be developed by practicing writing constantly. Writing either can be started from kindergarten time or at school from the first grade.

Choosing adequate time to write is one of the essential clues of effective writing. But, according to surveys, nowadays most language learners spend little time for writing. They need to learn this skill in order to become effective writers in the future. Teachers usually check and observe the way their students write, they can find difficulties of this skill for students and certainly they can help to correct mistakes and developing their writing skills.

According to the facts, at least 30 minutes should be devoted to writing and developing this skill for children in kindergarten. In order to become successful writer in the future the students should be taught from their early grades, exactly from kindergarten, when they begin to play with the pen or pencil.

In kindergarten, firstly, teachers should start to teach their children how to hold pen and pencil comfortably between their fingers. Although many teachers do not pay attention to this instruction it should be taught at that time, since it may discourage children from writing.

Likewise, teachers should show efficient ways of forming letter and how to write them easily. Children should practice each letter for 5-6 times in order to save it in their memory.

Additionally writing exercises should be practiced together with spelling in kindergarten. Spelling is as important as writing. But young learners may have some difficulties with spelling. In this case, teachers may use some useful activities. They can encourage the young learners to invent spelling at first, and then they correct misspelled words. Here the teacher can use very simple activity for spelling: a teacher shows some pictures, pronounces the sounds and describes targeted sound, then a teacher names each letter in turn and then writes them on the board. Students copy out the word onto their paper and repeat it many times. By this way children both see the picture and learn new word and spelling of that word as well. If the teachers can develop children's writing and spelling skills at kindergarten by making activities or anyhow, this will help them at school in their near future and they will continue without any difficulties of writing and spelling. Since, at their early age children tend to learn quickly. So that the teachers should be attentive and sensible!

"The schoolchildren at the 1st and 2nd grades should be informed some strategies of writing. Teachers should begin the course with basic skills such as reading aloud, which forces the student to focus on each word and draws attention to errors. Then teachers may move on teaching with other targeted strategies. At the 3rd grade, students may learn how to use dictionaries in order to determine the spelling of the words that they do not know. The learners may create their own dictionaries that are full of the words they found from dictionaries in order to learn and to spell correctly.

The learners need clear instructions as well, about how to form correct sentences and use them in their writing. Sentence instructions should move students from simple sentences to complex ones. In order to simplify to make complex sentences, the teachers can make some excerpts from children's life or children's newspapers or magazines. For instance:

The sentence frames can be used there to start with the simple sentences and move to complex sentences step by step, here is a sample activity for the sentence framing:

Sample activity: Sentence framing

Have students use the sentence frame to construct their own sentences and then share with their peers fulfilled sentences. Discuss their word choices.

I love _____ .

I love _____ and my _____ .

When my teacher _____ , I _____ .

My friend was _____ , but he _____ .

I am going _____ , and in the future _____ .

Sample Activity: Sentence expanding

Add words to the sentence using different parts of speech.

I like apples. I like red apples. I like red, big apples. I like red, big, tasty apples.

My cat is small. My cat is small and cute. My cat is small, cute, and white female cat.

Sample Activity: Sentence combining

The learners are to combine the simple sentences as one sentence and compare with others which sentence sounds better.

Lucia was playing a ball on the road. Lucia was careless. The car was coming.

When the car was coming, Lucia was playing a ball carelessly.

The three things: handwriting, spelling, and sentence construction are the most important and basic skills that teacher must pay attention while teaching writing

As in handwriting the students are taught how to form letters, in spelling part, pronunciation of words and letters, and in sentence construction part the effectiveness of sentence making instructions.

The learners should know that writing can be used for variety of purposes such as letter to someone, sharing an idea, providing with information or providing with entertainment etc. Learning how to write for different purposes can be useful not only at school but also for active participation in social life.

We have observed some strategies and practices for kindergarten and schoolchildren above to develop writing skills at this stage. Since writing is a complex process, it is separated into 2 sections, such as teaching how to apply the writing process, and teaching writing for variety of purposes.

The strategy is planned in series of actions for achieving something. It can be either physical or mental actions or both of them. These strategies of writing are the tools which can help students to understand the components of writing process. Many strategies can be used to help students with more than one part of the writing process. For example, if student is going to write a letter, at first he may set goals from his writing with some reasons.

In POW (pick, organize, write) strategy □ students decide about what they are going to write. They should brainstorm their ideas, opinions and make a plan. Then write it down according to your plan.

In drafting: make your sentences orally before writing it to your paper. Make many variants of your sentence and choose the most appropriate one. Pay attention to your topic sentences.

In sharing part: read your letter aloud to your partners, peers and listen to theirs too. Ask them what they liked on your letter and give your feedback to them too.

Evaluating: evaluate your letter yourself! Answer these questions:

Are your ideas clear? Does it acquire a good beginning, ending and middle part? Is there connection in your writing with the reader?

Revise and edit: Put punctuation marks, commas, end-of-sentence marks, question marks where necessary.

Check spellings of all your words!

When the students learn to use writing strategies, the teachers should discuss when and how to use the strategies throughout the writing process, as well as why the strategies are helpful. The teachers should help the students understand how to select appropriate strategies and use them across a range of writing tasks.[9. p125]

There can be different purposes for writing. A student should understand the purpose and then can select the way of the writing to the given task. For example the purpose of a complaint letter to complain about something or someone. Or purpose of information letter to provide you with the information that you may be needed. A letter can be written to persuade someone to do something, to narrate an event to a friend, or to inform a family member about an upcoming event.

Describing a person, place, or process with detailed description;

Narrating about a story that you have experienced; it can be real story or you may create yourself, fairytales that you know or heard from someone, poems and short stories.

Informing about something; new information or examine previously learned information. It can be about newspaper articles, science, letters, instructions or directions.

Persuading: giving strong opinions in order to catch the reader's attention and to convince the reader.

As concluding the theme, I can say that, Writing is a basic skill that can be developed by practicing over and over, without pausing . Every human skill gets better with constant, repetitive practice. With the help and enhance of teachers students may become better practitioners as the time passes. The teachers play a great role in the developing and education process of their students as the basic knowledge is given by them. Especially teaching writing from the early grades is important at school. As in future our society needs professional writers in every sphere. I have given my recommendations about writing and my personal advice, from my point of view, besides some useful activities related to writing as well. I hope, all these instructions will help you in education sphere, while teaching writing.

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